

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

WHAT ARE THE EXPECTATIONS OF WOMEN FROM THEIR SURROUNDINGS DURING PREGNANCY

Polotbek kyzy Akshyrman

*Master's student at the Institute of Social Sciences, Pedagogy Department
Department of Psychological and Pedagogical Support and Counseling
Kyrgyz-Turkish Manas University
Kyrgyzstan, Bishkek*

Efilit Erkan

Assoc. Prof. Dr.

*Faculty of Humanities, Department of Pedagogy
Department of Psychological and Pedagogical Support and Counseling
Kyrgyz-Turkish Manas University
Kyrgyzstan, Bishkek*

ORCID NO: 0000-0003-1158-5764

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to explore the expectations of women from their surroundings during pregnancy. It aims to understand the emotional, physical, and social support women seek from their family, friends, and healthcare professionals during this critical period. The study also aims to evaluate how these expectations influence their pregnancy experience and overall well-being. A qualitative research model was employed in this study. The study group consists of 22 pregnant women between the ages of 18 and 40. Data was collected through the "Semi-Structured Interview Form" developed by the researcher. The data were analyzed using descriptive and content analysis techniques, which are commonly used in qualitative research.

Keywords: pregnancy expectations, pregnancy experience, pregnancy challenges

Introduction

The purpose of every living being is to endure for the future. Each species ensures its continuity and secures its existence through the reproductive function. In humans, this function is carried out by the male and female reproductive organs, allowing species-specific characteristics to be transmitted from generation to generation without alteration [1].

All living beings in the world possess unique reproductive abilities. In humans, reproduction occurs through the sexual union of a man and a woman, where the female reproductive cell, the ovum (egg), merges with the male reproductive cell, the sperm. This fusion of chromosomes and implantation in the uterus result in fertilization (conception). Once the new cell, known as the zygote, forms, it enters a developmental period of approximately 10 months or 40 weeks, provided there are no health-threatening factors. This marks the beginning of pregnancy.

Pregnancy is divided into three stages called trimesters: the first trimester (the first three months), the second trimester (the middle three months), and the third trimester (the last three months). Each of these stages has its own unique physical and psychological developments, during which the zygote is sequentially referred to as an embryo and then a fetus [2].

Pregnancy is a unique, special, and deeply experiential process. Each month of pregnancy brings its own psychological concerns and expectations. The expectant mother undergoes a series of emotional and physical changes throughout the pregnancy. During this period, she may struggle to adapt to and accept the bodily and psychological changes occurring. On one

hand, she experiences the joy and excitement of bringing a child into the world; on the other, she faces concerns and expectations about the course of her pregnancy, the baby's health, childbirth, and postnatal care. Undoubtedly, the greatest expectation is to give birth to a healthy baby while also maintaining her own well-being. Therefore, while pregnancy can be a source of joy, maturity, self-expression, and a meaningful experience for some women, it can also be marked by anxiety, a restless wait, and a sense of burden for others.

In their study, Akbaş et al. [3] stated that pregnancy significantly impacts women and can create lasting psychological changes. The pregnancy process, for some women, can be a source of happiness, maturity, and self-realization, while for others, it can bring about negative emotions such as anxiety, emotional overload, and a state of anxious anticipation. Particularly in high-risk pregnancies, women may face more stress and anxiety. In this context, a study conducted by Aydın et al. [4] highlights the positive effects of music therapy on managing stress in high-risk pregnancies. Music therapy was found to reduce stress and anxiety levels in pregnant women, balance vital signs, and improve fetal health. Both studies demonstrate that pregnancy has significant physical and psychological effects, and managing these effects can be achieved through appropriate therapeutic approaches. Therefore, applying psychological support and stress management strategies in high-risk pregnancies is of critical importance for the health of the expectant mothers and the birth process.

When comparing the developmental processes of men and women, the most fundamental difference emerges as the pregnancy period. Having a child impacts both men and women, assigning them the roles of

parents. However, for women, the journey to motherhood is far more challenging than the fatherhood process for men. Pregnancy and childbirth represent one of the most significant changes in a woman's life. Physiological, hormonal, and psychological changes play an active role, and entering a period that requires preparation—where life is perceived as never being the same again—is considered a developmental crisis from a psychological perspective. While crises are temporary, their outcomes depend on how they are managed. Maintaining psychological and physical health and successfully adapting to this transformation can turn the crisis into an opportunity and a source of happiness [5].

The arrival of a child is a profound and multifaceted phenomenon that extends from the individual to society. It not only contributes to the maturity of expectant parents in all aspects—both materially and emotionally—but also shapes their parental roles and the structure of the family institution, ultimately influencing the cultural, moral, and social norms of society. From the very beginning of this process, the most active and affected individuals are undoubtedly the mother and the baby. The physical and psychosocial health of both is equally important. However, the developmental and transformative experiences the expectant mother undergoes during pregnancy are among the most profound and rapid changes an adult can experience [6]. This developmental stage is an adaptation period that the expectant mother must successfully navigate to maintain her physical, social, and psychological well-being [7].

During this adaptation period, pregnant women develop various expectations from their surroundings, especially from their spouses, families, colleagues, and most importantly, their healthcare providers monitoring their pregnancy.

Pregnancy is a time when expectant mothers become more sensitive, emotional, and prone to mood swings. Along with emotional changes, physical transformations also increase their expectations from their spouses. They may hope that their partners will share and experience similar emotions. For instance, an expectant mother may wish for her spouse to be as excited as she is about their baby's arrival. She may also expect her spouse to dedicate as much time and effort to her as they do to other aspects of life [8].

The support women receive from their surroundings during this process is a critical factor that can positively impact both their own and their baby's health. Therefore, understanding the needs and expectations of pregnant women is not only essential for individual well-being but also for shaping public health policies.

Pregnancy is often considered a crisis period in a woman's life, requiring adaptation to new and changing roles. Interestingly, in Chinese, the word for "crisis" also means "opportunity." This suggests that, besides being a stressful experience, pregnancy can also be an opportunity for personal growth, self-awareness, and creativity [9].

The need for support during pregnancy can be categorized into three main areas: Emotional Support – Critical for maintaining mental health, emotional support helps reduce stress, share fears, and provide a sense of security. Spouses and family members play a crucial role in offering this support. Physical Support – Involves assistance with daily tasks to ease the expectant mother's routine. Particularly in later stages of pregnancy, help with household chores and basic needs becomes essential. Social Support – Ensures that women do not feel isolated in their societal roles. Support from friends and neighbors helps them feel valued and understood.

In the study conducted by Zeliha and Gülden [10], the findings emphasize that food cravings predict eating attitudes, and that body image coping strategies play a partial mediating role in this relationship. During pregnancy, women may experience difficulties with their perceptions of their changing bodies. At this point, the importance of body image coping strategies becomes more apparent. Throughout the pregnancy, applying coping strategies to develop a healthy body image, improve eating attitudes, and maintain balanced food cravings becomes critical. Every woman experiences pregnancy differently. Reactions to pregnancy vary depending on past experiences, fears, social and economic conditions, and personal desires [11].

A review of the literature reveals that women seek psychological, physiological, and sociological support from their environment during pregnancy. Based on these findings, the research problem of this study is: What are the expectations of women from their surroundings during pregnancy?

Research Objective

The objective of this research is to determine the expectations of women from their surroundings during pregnancy.

Method

In this part of the research, the research model, study group, data collection tools, data collection process, and analysis and evaluation of the data are included. The research model has the characteristics of a qualitative study. A certain number of participants, considered sufficient for the research method, model, and data collection tool, were selected, and these participants constitute the study group of the research. The study group consists of 22 women between the ages of 20 and 34 in Kyrgyzstan in 2024. The data for the research were collected through the "Semi-Structured Interview Form" developed by the researcher. The data of the study were collected using a semi-structured interview form developed by the researcher. The study was analyzed using descriptive and content analysis techniques, which are a type of qualitative data analysis.

Results

The findings related to the participants' physical experiences during pregnancy are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Physical experiences		
Participants	Answers	f
K1, K2, K3, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K14, K15, K16, K17, K18, K19, K20, K21, K22	Fatigue	22
K2, K3, K4, K5, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K15, K16, K17, K18, K19, K21, K22	Nausea	18
K1, K2, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K11, K12, K13, K14, K15, K18, K21, K22	Cravings	16
K1, K3, K4, K6, K8, K10, K11, K12, K15, K16, K18, K19, K21	Back pain	13
K2, K4, K5, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K13, K14, K15, K17, K20	Movement restriction	13
K3, K6, K12, K15, K16, K18, K20, K21, K22	Insomnia	9
K1, K5, K12, K13, K16, K20, K21, K22	Skin changes	8
K1, K3, K12, K17, K18, K19	Edema	6

When Table 1 is examined, it can be seen that all participants (22) reported experiencing fatigue during the pregnancy process. Participant K1 stated: "I feel constantly tired throughout the pregnancy. Even doing daily tasks becomes difficult because my energy is always low, and I get tired quickly." The majority of participants (18) also reported experiencing nausea. Participant K7 shared: "The most challenging part of my pregnancy was the nausea. I lost 5 kilograms in two months due to nausea, and it occurred 8-10 times a day." A large majority (16) also reported experiencing food cravings. Participant K1 mentioned: "I didn't have nausea during my pregnancy, but I constantly craved salty foods, so I ate dried food from the moment I woke up until I went to sleep." Some participants (13) reported experiencing back pain and restricted mobility. Participant K15 stated: "As my pregnancy progressed, my back pain became unbearable. Especially when sitting and standing, my movements were significantly restricted." Participant K8 noted: "As my belly grew, it became more difficult to move, and due to my back pain, I couldn't stand for long periods."

Several participants reported facing significant physical difficulties as their pregnancy progressed. One

participant (K8) stated, "As my belly grew, it became harder to move; I can't stand for long because of back pain." This highlights how increased body weight and postural changes during pregnancy can negatively impact physical mobility and comfort.

Insomnia was another frequently mentioned issue, with nine participants expressing difficulties related to sleep. For example, participant K6 shared, "Throughout my pregnancy, sleeplessness has been the biggest challenge for me. I can't find a comfortable position, and I wake up frequently to go to the bathroom." This suggests that both physiological and hormonal factors may disrupt sleep quality during pregnancy.

Skin-related issues and edema were also commonly reported. Eight participants noted various skin changes, such as discoloration, spots, and stretch marks. K13 remarked, "During pregnancy, I developed discoloration and spots on my skin. I also started getting stretch marks on my belly. Even though I use moisturizer, I couldn't prevent the changes."

The findings related to emotional experiences during pregnancy are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Emotional experiences during pregnancy		
Participants	Answers	f
K1, K2, K3, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K14, K15, K16, K17, K18, K19, K20, K21, K22	Excitement	22
K1, K2, K3, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K14, K15, K17, K18, K19, K21, K22	Anxiety	20
K1, K2, K4, K5, K6, K7, K9, K10, K11, K13, K14, K15, K16, K17, K19, K21, K22	Happiness	17
K1, K2, K4, K6, K7, K8, K9, K11, K13, K14, K15, K18, K19	Sensitivity	13
K2, K4, K5, K6, K7, K9, K10, K12, K14, K15, K16, K18, K21	Impatience	13
K1, K2, K4, K6, K7, K8, K10, K13, K15, K16, K17, K20	Insecurity	12
K2, K3, K5, K6, K9, K10, K12, K14, K15, K18	Fear	10
K2, K4, K7, K9, K12, K13, K19, K20,	Stress	8

When Table 2 is examined, it is evident that all participants (22) reported experiencing excitement during the pregnancy process. K2: "When I learned that I was going to be a mother for the first time, I felt an incredible excitement. This feeling made me both happy and caused impatience."

The majority of participants (18) also expressed feeling anxiety during the pregnancy process. K5: "I am

very afraid that something might go wrong during labor. I constantly worry about my baby's health."

A large majority (17) stated that they felt happiness during the process. K13: "The thought of becoming a mother made me very happy. This happiness increased even more when I felt my baby's first movements."

The findings related to the most needed type of support during pregnancy are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

The most needed type of support related to pregnancy		
Participants	Answers	f
K1, K2, K3, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K14, K15, K16, K17, K18, K19, K20, K21, K22	Emotional Support	22
K2, K3, K4, K5, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K15, K16, K17, K18, K19, K21, K22	Physical Assistance	18
K2, K4, K5, K7, K8, K9, K13, K15, K18, K22	Medical Information	10
K4, K10, K11, K14, K17, K20	Social Support	6

When Table 3 is examined, all participants (22) reported that they needed emotional support during the pregnancy process. K12 stated: "Having my spouse and family by my side during this period has been incredibly comforting. Without their support, I wouldn't have felt as well and relaxed as I do." The majority of participants (18) also indicated a need for physical assistance.

K21 shared: "In the last few months, I've even struggled to put on my shoes. My husband helps a lot with the housework—otherwise, I would have had a really hard time."

The data regarding the expectations of pregnant women from doctors and nurses in outpatient clinics are presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

Expectations of pregnant women from doctors and nurses in outpatient clinics

Participants	Answers	f
K1, K8, K9, K14, K10, K4, K14, K17, K19, K22	Should be friendly	10
K2, K5, K12, K18, K21	Should provide information	5
K3, K7, K11	Should be attentive	3
K20, K15	Should answer questions	2
K16, K13	Should be able to show empathy	2

When Table 4 is examined, some participants (10) stated that healthcare professionals should be friendly. K9: "It is very important for healthcare professionals to be friendly towards us. It makes me feel more comfortable."

K5: "I want to receive accurate information about pregnancy in the most reliable way from healthcare professionals." K6: "Whenever I have a question, it is very important for me to receive clear and detailed information."

A portion of the participants (5) emphasized that healthcare professionals should provide information.

The findings regarding pregnant women's expectations from their surroundings are presented in Table 5.

Table 5.

Pregnant women's expectations from their surroundings		
Participants	Answers	f
K1, K2, K3, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K14, K15, K16, K17, K18, K19, K20, K21, K22	Understanding and Patience	22
K2, K3, K4, K5, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K13, K15, K16, K17, K18, K19, K21	Physical Support	16
K1, K3, K4, K5, K7, K8, K9, K11, K13, K15, K18	Emotional Encouragement and Motivation	11
K2, K5, K6, K12, K14, K20	Financial Support	6

When Table 5 is examined, it is evident that all participants (22) stated that they expected understanding and patience from those around them during pregnancy. K17: "What I need the most during this period is for everyone to better understand me and be patient."

The majority of participants (16) expressed that they expected physical support, especially in household chores and daily activities. K21: "Receiving help from my spouse and family in housework really made me feel more comfortable."

Approximately half of the participants (11) indicated that they expected those around them to create a positive atmosphere and provide moral encouragement throughout the pregnancy process. K9: "Hearing motivational and supportive words during difficult times meant a lot to me."

Result and Discussion

In this section of the research, the physical experiences of women during pregnancy have been analyzed, and the findings have been compared with other studies in the literature. According to the findings, the most frequently reported physical experience among the participants was fatigue. All 22 women in the study expressed experiencing fatigue throughout their pregnancy.

Nausea was mentioned by 18 participants and emerged as the second most frequent physical experience, following fatigue. Cravings were reported by 16 participants, and there are various findings in the literature suggesting that this phenomenon can arise from both physiological and psychological factors. Back

pain and restricted mobility were mentioned by 13 participants each, and these experiences were associated with increased weight and postural changes in the later stages of pregnancy. Other less frequently reported experiences included insomnia (9 participants), skin changes (8 participants), and edema (6 participants).

The most frequently reported emotional experience was excitement, expressed by all participants. The participants stated that this emotion was strongly felt during the process of witnessing the beginning of a new life and embarking on the journey of motherhood. However, the feeling of anxiety was mentioned by 20 participants and emerged as another significant emotion frequently experienced during pregnancy. This finding can be related to the concerns expectant mothers have about their own and their babies' health. Happiness was expressed by 17 participants and was considered one of the positive aspects of the pregnancy process, along with excitement. Sensitivity and impatience were reported by 13 participants, respectively. Emotional fluctuations caused by hormonal changes lead to increased sensitivity and emotional reactivity in women during pregnancy. Impatience, on the other hand, can be associated with the desire of expectant mothers to hold their babies as soon as possible. In conclusion, understanding the emotional experiences during pregnancy can contribute to the development of strategies to help expectant mothers navigate this process in a healthier manner. In this context, increasing emotional support during pregnancy will not only enhance the emotional well-being of expectant mothers but also facilitate the process of preparing for childbirth.

In the study, the types of services expected by pregnant women from doctors and nurses in outpatient clinics were examined. The most common expectation among participants was that doctors and nurses should be friendly and approachable. Ten participants stated that a cheerful and friendly attitude from healthcare professionals helped them feel more comfortable during the pregnancy process. Providing information was mentioned by five participants and was considered an important aspect of their expectations from healthcare professionals. The participants emphasized the importance of having access to accurate information during pregnancy. Being attentive was mentioned by three participants. Pregnant women expressed the need for healthcare professionals to dedicate time to listen to their questions and understand their needs. Less frequently expressed expectations included answering questions (mentioned by two participants) and demonstrating empathy (also mentioned by two participants). The uncertainties and concerns during pregnancy increase the need for clear and compassionate answers to questions. Furthermore, the ability to demonstrate empathy means that doctors and nurses understand the emotional state of the pregnant women and approach them with more sensitivity. In conclusion, the expectations of pregnant women from doctors and nurses in outpatient clinics provide valuable insights for improving the quality of healthcare services and supporting the psychological and physical well-being of women during pregnancy. Strengthening healthcare professionals'

approaches to emotional support and information provision will contribute to helping pregnant women navigate this process in a healthier and safer manner.

According to the research results, the type of support most needed by pregnant women during pregnancy is emotional support. All participants (22 individuals) stated that emotional support is an indispensable need for them during the pregnancy process. Physical assistance was mentioned by 18 participants and was the second most needed type of support after emotional support. The difficulty in daily life activities during pregnancy increases the importance of physical support.

This research on the expectations of women from their surroundings during pregnancy reveals that the most common expectation is understanding and patience. All participants (22 individuals) stated that they expect understanding and patience from their environment. Considering that pregnancy is a physically and emotionally challenging period, this highlights the importance of emotional support and a patient approach from the environment. The literature suggests that during pregnancy, women's emotional needs intensify and that environmental support can help make this period healthier.

Physical support was mentioned by 16 participants, indicating a need for physical assistance during pregnancy. As the pregnancy progresses, women tend to seek more physical help and support. Expectations for moral and motivational support were expressed by 11 participants. They expressed a desire to receive emotional encouragement and motivation from their surroundings. Since pregnancy involves emotional ups and downs, the positive and encouraging attitude of those around them can improve the mood of pregnant women. Financial support was mentioned by 6 participants. Pregnancy may bring some financial challenges, and expectant mothers may seek support from their surroundings in this regard. Expectations for personal space and freedom were expressed by 4 participants. This indicates that pregnant women want their physical and emotional boundaries to be respected, and they desire their personal space to be maintained. Finally, expectations for accurate information and guidance were expressed by 3 participants. Having correct information about pregnancy is especially important for first-time mothers. The lack of information can lead to anxiety and stress, so access to accurate and reliable information helps expectant mothers make more informed decisions. Pregnancy is a distinct process, birth is another, and providing support for raising a child to adulthood brings its own set of challenges. During pregnancy, intense physical changes and psychological fluctuations occur, along with various positive emotions such as love, compassion, trust, excitement, hope, patience, and gratitude. One of the most profound aspects of the pregnancy process for an expectant mother is the fact that a living being is growing in her body and will soon enter the world. This is a miraculous, awe-inspiring process for a pregnant woman, forming a direct connection with the Creator, through which she feels His love, trust, and support. This experience not

only impacts the woman herself but also everyone witnessing the process of a woman becoming a mother, evoking awe and excitement. Therefore, showing interest and providing support to an expectant mother is a rewarding and positive gesture. This research was conducted with the motivation to shed light on the psychosocial-spiritual development that pregnant women experience during this process and to help take steps that will improve their pregnancy experiences based on the findings. In conclusion, understanding the expectations of women from their surroundings during pregnancy is important for improving the quality of support provided during this period. Meeting the support needs of pregnant women will help them have a healthier pregnancy and provide them with greater strength in the post-birth process.

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